

ANALYTICAL AND FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSES ON RELIABILITY OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS

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Abstract

Long-term safety and reliability of composite structures has long been an active research subject. An early study by Robinson [1,2] shows the safety factor (SF) value of 2.3 for carbon-epoxy composite based on the experimental tests on the early carbon-fibre composites. Later, this study was applied to establish the burst pressure ratio for compressed-natural gas (CNG) composite pressure vessels (CPVs) in 1980s. The current study performed a new stress rupture analysis on unidirectional (UD) carbon-epoxy laminates fabricated by advanced composite material nowadays. Two different approaches were applied to characterise lifetime performance of composite materials: analytical and finite element approaches. The scatters of intrinsic properties of composite constituents resulting in variable long-term lifetime were revealed. Using the lifetime results, the safety margins for the carbon-epoxy composites necessary for obtaining a lifetime of 15 years and failure rate of 10^{-6} were determined, and the results obtained by the two approaches are in agreement. Compared to the Robinson's study (i.e. 2.3 for SF), a reduced SF value to 1.4 was obtained for the current advanced carbon-fibre composite materials. This study supports a need of re-evaluating the values of efficient safety margin for composite pressure vessel cylinders.

1 General Introduction

Fibre-reinforced polymer material has been increasingly applied in high-strength application structures for the replacement of classical metal material due to its high specific mechanical properties. Composite pressure vessels have been widely applied in the storage of compressed natural gas on road vehicles, replacing heavy-weight metal cylinders. In the recent years, high performance

carbon fibre CPVs are developed for the storage of compressed hydrogen at high pressure as the supply to a fuel cell (hydrogen energy). Nevertheless, one of the most important concerns for composite technology is the long-term behaviour of structures, the failure of which could often prove to be catastrophic. Composite behaviour and failure is different from that seen with metal structures. Although composite materials have been widely applied in many commercial structural applications, too often tests and standards used for composite structures have just been taken from standards developed for metal or other traditional structural materials. Whereas these standards can often be justified for traditional materials, in terms of known failure processes, the mechanisms involved in the damage of composite structures are often radically different. For example, it is mandatory for each CPV to be approved by proof pressure testing before being put into service [3,4]. This was originally established for the certification of metallic cylinders. The traditional proof test involves pressurising cylinders to 1.5 times than the design pressure level. In a composite structure the high strength carbon fibres are wound over the mandrel, and support almost the entire pressure so the breakage of fibre filaments is the primary damage mechanism governing the degradation of composite materials. Although the proof test could verify liner leakage, it must be noticed that this test does not give any information on the actual state of damage of the cylinder. This indicates that if composite structures are to be used with confidence, the failure of such structures should be evaluated on their specific micromechanical degradation processes which ultimately control failure.

Many studies [1,2,5-7] have investigated long-term micromechanical degradation of composite material

subjected to tensile loading, in particular fibre failure. When unidirectional carbon-epoxy laminates are subjected to long-term sustained tensile loading, an increase in numbers of fibre breaks has been observed occurring at a slow rate [5,6]. Carbon fibre filaments are not susceptible to steady or dynamic tensile loading [7], indicating that the material strength of the fibres is not affected by loading time. In contrast, the viscoelasticity property of epoxy matrix can vary with time under tensile loads, which affects the load transfer mechanism in the composites. The time-dependent viscoelasticity of epoxy matrix has been determined to be the driving cause to the long-term fibre-rupturing process in UD laminates subjected to a steady load, even though the matrix only supports a fraction of the entire tensile load.

Blassiau and colleagues modelled the effect of the viscoelasticity of the epoxy matrix on the fibre-failure process in UD laminates subjected to sustained tensile loading, using a two-scale FE (FE^2) model [8-13]. When carbon fibre breakages developed in the laminate, the shear deformation at the interfaces of the broken fibres and the surrounding matrix caused the broken fibres to be reloaded, which formed a discrete damage zone. Within the zone, the intact fibres neighbouring the break experienced an increase in stress over a short length, such that the total stress within the zone remained unchanged, and the overstressing effect on the adjacent intact fibres could lead to their failure. When the laminate was subjected to sustained tensile loading, viscoelastic relaxation of the epoxy matrix occurred. The reduction to the shear modulus of the matrix then caused a decline in the efficiency of the load transfer mechanism in the composites. As a result, the extent of local damage zones associated with existing fibre breaks enlarged and more fibre breaks were likely to develop within the damage zone, forming clusters of fibre breaks. The observation of the fibre-rupturing process by Blassiau using the FE^2 model was validated by the study of Scott et al. [14-16]. Using ultra high-resolution computed tomography, Scott et al. observed clustering process of fibre breaks in 0° plies of carbon-epoxy specimens subjected to increasing tensile loading as close to failure.

Camara and colleagues showed that the accumulation of fibre breakage in UD carbon-epoxy laminates could trigger the failure of the laminates, using the FE^2 model [6]. At the same applied stress level, the lifetimes for UD laminates subjected to a stress rupture test were seen to be variable. This is due to the stochastic nature of fibre strengths and the effect of the arrangement of the individual fibres within the composites [6]. The intrinsic properties of composite constituents have critical effect on long-term lifetime performance of composites. The study concluded that accumulation of fibre breaks governs the structural integrity of the composites laminates. Based on the same philosophy, Robinson performed a stress rupture analysis on carbon-fibre strand reinforced polymer specimens [1,2]. Variable time-to-ruptures for the composites were determined in the stress rupture test and a probability analysis was performed to characterise the distribution of the lifetime with respect to the applied stress level. Safety factor (SF) value of 2.3 was determined for carbon fibre composites, associated to the lifetime of 15 years and a failure probability of 10^{-6} [1,2]. The work of Robinson has been used as a fundamental basis to establish the burst pressure ratio (BPR) for CNG CPV cylinders.

As composite technology advances with time, the material properties of the constituents of composites and manufacturing processes have significantly improved, which should improve the lifetime performance of composite structures. Important to note, the study of Robinson was based on the experimental results obtained with very early carbon fibres produced in 1970s, and the proposed safety factor value for the early carbon-epoxy composites materials may no longer be appropriate for the advanced composite material nowadays. Therefore, the goal of this study was to present a new evaluation analysis on the lifetime performance of current carbon fibre reinforced polymer materials.

Unlike the typical stress rupture analysis (e.g. in Robinson's study [1,2]), two approaches, based on analytical and FE techniques, were developed, allowing a time-efficient stress rupture analysis. Three techniques are all based on the same philosophy but use different ways to estimate residual lifetime of the composites. For the analytical approach, a probability analysis was

performed on the estimated lifetimes of UD carbon-epoxy specimens obtained from the modified stress rupture analysis; the lifetime was estimated by dividing the number of damage events at failure of the composite recorded by AE over the damage accumulation rate. For the FE approach, the stress rupture lifetimes of the specimens were calculated using the FE² model developed by Blassiau and colleagues [5, 8-13]. The stochastic nature of fibre strength and variable arrangement of individual fibres were used in modeling carbon-epoxy laminates and seen to be the cause of variable lifetimes. The distributions of lifetime was then characterised using probability analysis. The safety factors associated with lifetimes of 15 years and a failure rate of 10^{-6} were calculated. Finally, a comparison of SF values for carbon-epoxy materials between the Robinson's study, the analytical analysis and FE analysis of this study was performed.

The models used for the simulations describing stress rupture test (i.e. sustained tensile loading-to-rupture) has been described in detail elsewhere [8-10,13].

2 Lifetime Evaluation using FE approach

2.1 Description of [0°] carbon-epoxy laminates

The [0°] specimens were modelled using the fibre rupture FE² model developed by Blassiau and colleagues [8-13].

The material system studied S was a prismatic specimen. The specimen considered was taken to be a plate delimited by the following surfaces:

- S_{-a} situated at $x_1=-a$ and S_{+a} situated at $x_1=+a$;
- S_{-b} situated at $x_2=-b$ and S_{+b} situated at $x_2=+b$;
- S_{-c} situated at $x_3=-c$ and S_{+c} situated at $x_3=+c$;

The long axis of the specimens was described by the vector x_1 . The width was oriented by the vector x_2 and the thickness by the vector x_3 . The plane of the specimens was defined by the vectors x_1 and x_2 . The cross-section of the specimen was defined by the vectors x_2 and x_3 . The dimensions of the laminate are 64 mm in length (2a), 5mm in wide (2b) and 0.8 mm in thick (2c). The thickness of each ply of the laminates was 0.1 mm. The fibre volume fraction of

the specimen was assumed to be homogenous with the average V_f of 64%. A total number of 6750 C3D8 eight-node brick elements were used to construct the laminate model.

For the boundary conditions used in the simulations, a uniform stress was applied to the surfaces S_{+a} and S_{-a} of the specimen and a uniform zero force was applied to the other surfaces. A stress rupture test on [0°] specimen was modelled; this involved tensile loading the specimen to the designated stress level at a loading rate of 1 MPa/s and then maintaining it at the peak level until final failure. The lifetimes of the specimens were determined in the stress rupture simulations. Six different designated stress levels were calculated: 2581 MPa, 2595.5 MPa, 2610 MPa, 2668 MPa, 2726 MPa, and 2784 MPa (associated to 89%, 89.5%, 90%, 92%, 94%, and 96% of the average tensile failure stress, respectively). For each stress level, 100 simulations of the stress rupture test were performed in order to obtain a meaningful number of lifetime results for probability analysis. In the simulations, the local distribution of fibre strength in the RVE was randomly altered using a Monte-Carlo algorithm. The time-to-ruptures were calculated and the distribution of the lifetime was studied using probability analysis.

2.2 Lifetime Results Calculated by FE approach

When the local distribution of fibre strength at the microscopic scale was randomly changed using a Monte Carlo simulation there were large variations in the calculated lifetime values. Fig. 1 shows that the lifetime results showed a Weibull distribution. Associated to different applied stress levels, the functions describing the lifetime time with respect to the failure rate and lifetime were determined, and using the functions, the failure life of [0°] laminates for the failure probability value of 10^{-6} were calculated for the different stress levels. Fig. 2 shows the relationship between the calculated lifetime associated to the failure probability of 10^{-6} and the applied tensile load level, and the function describing this relationship was determined. A log-linear increase in the lifetime was found with decreasing the applied tensile load level. From this, the minimal applied load level necessary for obtaining the failure probability of 10^{-6} and the designated lifetime can be determined.

3. Lifetime Evaluation using Analytical Approach

3.1 Description of the Modified Stress Rupture

Test with AE monitoring

Unidirectional carbon-epoxy laminate plates were made by filament winding technique with Toray T700 carbon fibres and LY564/ARADUR917/960-1 epoxy matrix. From these laminate plates, the $[0^\circ]$ specimens with dimensions of 150 mm in gauge length, 20 mm in wide, and 0.8 mm in thick were fabricated. The average tensile failure stress for these specimens was about 3023 MPa.

The stress rupture test was modified to a three-stage tensile loading test the purpose of which was to estimate the lifetime of the laminates within a limited testing time; first the specimen was monotonically loaded to the designated applied load level at a loading rate of 30 N/s using INSTRON electrical-powered testing machine, then maintained at the peak load level for 20 hours. After the steady loading phase, the specimen was reloaded from the given applied load level at a loading rate of 30N/s until final failure. Six different levels of tensile load were studied in the stress rupture test: 84%, 86%, 88%, 90%, 92% and 95% of the average failure load level. Two replica tests were performed for each load level (except for the 90%, 92%, and 95% cases).

Acoustic emission recorded composite damage events during the stress rupture test. AE acquisition system of PCI-2 made by Physical Acoustic Cooperation (PAC) was applied. Two AE transducers of $\mu 80$ made by PAC were applied to facilitate linear location algorithm calculation. The transducers were placed at +25 mm and -25 mm from the centre of the specimen, respectively. When acoustic noises of composite damage were recorded, the detected signals were amplified with a gain of 40 dB using preamplifier of 2/4/6 (made by PAC). Table 1 shows the acquisition setup applied in the AE analysis.

3.2 Lifetime Results Estimated by Analytical Approach

3.2.1 Analytical estimation of the minimal lifetime for $[0^\circ]$ laminates

The lifetime of $[0^\circ]$ laminates was estimated from the total number of damage events measured at failure (i.e. damage threshold level) divided by the

damage accumulation rate. When the specimen was subjected to a steady load, the AE results (Fig. 3) shows that the number of AE hits increased at a log-linear rate with loading time, and the damage accumulation could be characterised as a function of time. Using the determined damage accumulation function, it becomes possible to predict further damage and then to calculate the remaining lifetime with respect to the damage threshold level. Depending on the value of the applied stress level at failure, the damage threshold level could vary; the specimen ruptured by increasing tensile loading should contain lower numbers of fibre breaks than that seen with sustained tensile loading-to-rupture where a lower peak stress level was applied to the specimen at failure. In this study, the damage threshold level was defined as the total number of AE hits recorded at final failure, caused by increasing tensile loading, which is the minimal level of damage threshold. Therefore, the lifetime calculated using this approach was assumed to be the minimal lifetime for the specimens.

3.2.2 Statistical characterisation of specimens' lifetime

Fig. 4 shows the distribution of the estimated lifetime points for $[0^\circ]$ specimens subjected to different steady load levels. The normalised load level 1 (σ_{norm1}) is calculated by the applied load level over the average failure load level. A linear relationship between $\ln(\text{estimated lifetime})$ and σ_{norm1} was obtained. However, several outliers of the lifetime points were found, which were due to the variability of laminate strength; when the actual laminate strength was much higher or lower than the average value, the calculated lifetime points would be deviated from the linear relationship and outliers formed.

A master lifetime function was determined to characterise the distribution of estimated lifetime points for $[0^\circ]$ specimens. The normalised load level 2 (σ_{norm2}) calculated by the applied load level of the given specimen over its actual failure load level was defined. Using the σ_{norm2} , it was found in Fig. 5 that all the estimated lifetime points conformed well to the log-linear relationship, independent of the variability of laminate strength. The function

describing this relationship is determined as the master lifetime function.

As discussed, when the distribution of the estimated lifetime results was analysed using the average failure stress level, the difference between the average and actual failure stress level of $[0^\circ]$ specimens produced the scatter of lifetime points (shown in Fig. 4). Nevertheless, each lifetime result point could be associated with one log-linear lifetime curve, which has a constant value of gradient (same as the master lifetime curve) but different constant term b . The constant term b controls the translation of lifetime curves, related to the variation in tensile strength of the specimens and can be calculated using equation 1. Fig. 6 shows the statistical distribution of b value calculated for each lifetime result points as shown in Fig. 4. Since the change to the b values was related to the material strength of the specimens, a probability analysis was performed on the distribution of the b values so as to statistically characterise the variation in the material strength. For the probability of 10^{-6} , the b values was calculated as 372.4 and therefore the lifetime function of $[0^\circ]$ specimens associated to the failure probability of 10^{-6} is $\ln(\text{estimated lifetime}) = -490.1\sigma_{norm2} + 372.4$.

$$\ln(\text{estimated lifetime}) = -490.1\sigma_{norm2} + b \quad (1)$$

Where σ_{norm2} represents percentage of sustained load level with respect to the average failure stress level, -490.1 is the value of the gradient obtained from the master lifetime curve, b is the translation parameter for lifetime curve, and *estimated lifetime* is measured in second.

4. Comparison of Lifetime Results between Analytical Estimations and FE Calculations

Fig. 7 shows the lifetime result curves, associated with a failure rate of 10^{-6} , obtained by the analytical and FE analyses. Both the analyses show that the lifetime increased at a log-linear rate as the σ_{norm1} decreased although the gradient values for the two lifetime curves were different (i.e. -490 ln(s) and -68 ln(s) for the analytical and FE results). The FE result shows a much better lifetime performance for $[0^\circ]$ specimens than the analytical result until the σ_{norm1} decreased to 0.72. This could be attributed to several factors. First, the viscoelasticity properties of epoxy

matrix used in the two analyses were not identical, which controlled long-term damage accumulation of fibre breakage in the material system. Second, the lifetime value calculated in the analytical analysis was based on the hypothesis of the minimal lifetime estimation whereas the FE calculated the actual lifetime for the specimen. Thirdly, other factors such as manufacturing defects could degrade the lifetime performance of $[0^\circ]$ specimens in the experiment whereas the FE did not consider those factors. A lower lifetime performance for the analytical analysis was expected.

Using the determined lifetime functions, the applied load levels for $[0^\circ]$ specimens necessary for obtaining a lifetime of 15 years with a failure rate of 10^{-6} were determined as 71.9% and 78.8% of the average failure stress by the analytical and FE analyses, respectively. The values of minimal intrinsic SF were calculated as 1.4 and 1.3, which only took into account variable intrinsic laminate strength. Compared to the Robinson's study [1,2], a significant improvement to the value of SF was found (SF by Robinson is 2.3), indicating the improvement in the lifetime performance of the current advanced composite materials. Since the safety margin for the CPV cylinders are established based on Robinson's study (associated to the early carbon fibre composites), these results supports an increasing concern of re-evaluating the values of efficient BPR for CPV cylinders fabricated by advanced composite materials nowadays.

For the storage of hydrogen fuel, thick-walled CPV cylinders with high-pressure performance are applied. Unlike the laminate specimens, complex-loading processes occurred in the cylinder when subjected to pressurisation, in particular variable hoop tensile stress and radial compressive stress in through-thickness direction. These loading processes can cause fibre failures in tension and in compression (i.e. normal to the fibre direction). A future study of lifetime performance on CPV cylinders could be performed using the FE² fibre rupture model based on the FE approach developed in this study.

5. Conclusion

Using FE and analytical approaches, tools for analysing long-term lifetime performance and capable of evaluating minimal safety margin required for UD carbon-epoxy laminates have been developed based on accumulation of intrinsic fibre breakage with respect to the threshold level, and the results of which were in agreement. It was found that unidirectional carbon-epoxy laminates that are loaded at less than 72% of the average failure stress will effectively last for 15 years with a failure rate of 10^{-6} so that the safety factor is around 1.4. Compared to Robinson's study which used early carbon-epoxy composite materials in 1970s, a significant improvement in lifetime performance was determined for carbon composite made with the advanced composite materials. These results supports that there is a need of re-evaluating safety margin of CPV cylinders manufactured nowadays since the BPR values of the cylinders were established based on the study of Robinson [1,2]. A new evaluation analysis of safety measures on the long-term usage of composite pressure vessels is required, which can be performed in future using fibre rupture FE² model

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Table 1: Acquisition setup for the AE test

Peak definition time (PDT)	50 μ s
Hit definition time (HDT)	100 μ s
Hit lock-out time (HLT)	200 μ s
Threshold level	40 dB
Analogue filter	0.1 MHz – 1 MHz

Fig. 1: Cumulative failure probability of UD carbon-epoxy laminates subjected to stress rupture test at 96% of the average failure load with respect to time-to-failure.

Fig. 2: Distribution of *calculated lifetime* for $[0^\circ]$ laminates subjected to stress rupture test. The σ_{norm1} was calculated by the applied tensile load level over the average tensile failure load level. The smoothing equation applied is $\ln(\text{calculated lifetime}) = -68.4\sigma_{norm1} + 73.9$.

Fig. 4: Distribution of *estimated lifetime* for $[0^\circ]$ laminates subjected to the modified stress rupture test. The σ_{norm1} was calculated by the applied tensile load level over the average tensile failure load level. The circle in dashed line marked the outliers of the lifetime result points.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3: (a) Cumulative number of AE hits for $[0^\circ]$ laminates subjected to sustained tensile loading at 88% of the average failure stress for the loading time of 75 hours (i.e. $2.7E5$ s). The smoothing result for the cumulative AE hit curve. (b) Cumulative number of AE hits for $[0^\circ]$ laminates with respect to $\ln(\text{Loading time})$.

Fig. 5: Distribution of *estimated lifetime* for [0°] laminates subjected to the modified stress rupture test. The σ_{norm2} was calculated by the applied tensile load level over the actual tensile failure load level, determined in the post tensile rupture test. The master lifetime function was determined as $\ln(\text{estimated lifetime}) = -490.1\sigma_{norm2} + 454.5$.

Fig. 6: Cumulative probability distribution of the parameter b used in the lifetime equation. A two-parameter Weibull function was applied to determine the function describing the distributions of b values. The smoothing equation applied is $CPD = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{b}{483.6}\right)^{52.8}\right)$.

Fig. 7: The lifetime curves associated to failure probability of 10^{-6} for [0°] laminates subjected to the stress rupture tests, determined by analytical and FE approaches. The figures on the LHS and RHS have different parameters of y-axes, which are $\ln(\text{calculated lifetime})$ and *calculated lifetime*, respectively.